

2021

Vehicular Pollution in Kolkata - An Empirical Study

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VEHICULAR POLLUTION IN KOLKATA – AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

A report Submitted to the University of Burdwan for the
Partial fulfilment of the requirement for the Degree of
Master of Law in
Social Outreach Programme (LMCT 402)

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LL.M (4th Semester)

Roll No BUR LLM (SEM) 2019/40

Reg. No. A72 of 2016-17

Session: 2019-2021

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Certificate of Supervisor

I have great pleasure in certifying that Sumanta Narayan Podder, a student of LL.M. 4th Semester in Hooghly Mohsin College P.G. Department of Law, and having Roll No - BUR LLM (SEM) 2019/40, Session - 2019-2021, Reg. No. A-72 of 2016-17, of University of Burdwan, has written his Social Outreach paper "*Vehicular Pollution in Kolkata - An Empirical Study*" under my supervision as partial fulfilment of LL.M. 4th Semester.

This is to certify that the candidate has done the work and I wish all success in life.

.....
Debabrata Basu

(Supervisor)

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SECTION – I

Prologue

In a megacity like Kolkata, the concern about burning fossil fuels through the engines of vehicles using petrol and diesel is high as the numbers of such vehicles are increasing day by day. Due to this the pollution levels are always ticking at their top levels or irreversibly crossing such levels which is fatal for all living organisms. But the modern civilization with its modern mode of production system has brought such hazards along with the comfort of high class-living and we are bound to be hit by their notorious and obnoxious effects. The quality of air in which we breathe, the temperature of atmosphere we live in, the acidity of the sea-water surrounding us, the loss of biodiversity due to us has multifarious ill effects towards the entire environment, ecology and nature, and we experience in various ways the anthropogenic damage of the nature. Be it like tsunami, or Amphan, or rising sea levels, or the very recent world-wide COVID-19 pandemic wreaking havoc; certainly, these are not directly created by humans, but these are the indirect effect of the acts of humans. Man has since capitalist scientific and technical revolution seen nature only as a source of his various productive forces. Never ever does he see himself and nature as organically linked. We forget at times that we are not above nature or superior to nature, or owners of nature. We are within nature and we are just caretakers of nature - caretakers for all the generations to come.

Rapid economic growth and urbanizations may have brought many benefits to India, but the environment and ecology has degraded, exposing the whole lot of Indian population to serious air pollution. The results of this pollution have led to poor urban air quality in many Indian cities, including Kolkata. The air pollution and the resulting air quality can surely be attributed to emissions from various means of modern-day transportation. The air quality has, therefore, been, an issue of concern for various developmental activities. There such pollutants that are responsible for the degradation of air quality in cities. The most watched pollutants include suspended particulate matter, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide and carbon dioxide. Due to the levels of pollution created by these, the ambient air quality in major cities in India has become very poor. The annual average concentration of PM₁₀ is very high in Indian cities. In

particular, many cities have exceeded the officially designated critical levels, including Kolkata.

SECTION – II

History of Air Pollution in Kolkata

Currently there is lot of discussions going on regarding the ambient air quality (AAQ) of Kolkata. The actual fact is that the debates concerning the air pollution in Kolkata is historically very old. If we are to understand the actual scenario of Air Pollution as well as the Vehicular Pollution of the city of Kolkata, we have to briefly go through this history.

The first Act regarding air pollution of the city of Kolkata and Howrah was passed by the British colonisers, in 1863, which was named as *Kolkata and Howrah Smoke Nuisance Act, 1863*¹. Before this, in the year 1853 this type of statute was enacted only in London. In 1879, a special committee was set up for the review of the situation of pollution in Kolkata. In 1902, Mr. Frederick Grover from Leeds came to Bengal as the Smoke Inspector of Kolkata and in 1905 *The Bengal Smoke Nuisance Act* was passed by the Crown.

The Air Pollution of the city of Kolkata can be divided into three categories: a) before 1855, the chief source of air pollution of Kolkata was from burning of woods, coal etc for domestic fuel use, and also from herbal oils and cow dung, b) after 1920, coal was being started to be used as a major fuel for households, and c) in 1855, after laying of rail line from Kolkata industrial region to Raniganj³, the use of coal as fuel was increased a manifold. Most of pollution was created by the looms alongside Hooghly river. Besides this, steamers, metal furnaces and effluents from the boilers of various mills and factories aggravated the scenario. In 1912, the total number of steam-boilers was 2039. In 1923 the number became 2582. In the third stage, the chief source of air pollution was from the burning of petrol as fuel of automobiles. Even if slowly,

¹ <https://abhilekh-patal.in/jspui/handle/123456789/984123>

² <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/coverage/smoke-laws-first-enacted-in-city-of-joy-30499>

³ [https://er.indianrailways.gov.in/view_section.jsp?fontColor=black&backgroundColor=LIGHTSTEELBLUE&lang=0&id=0,6,443,528,538#:~:text=February%201855%2C%20a%20train%20was,to%20Raniganj%20\(194%20Km\).&text=During%20the%20middle%20of%20nineteenth,owned%20by%20Sri%20Dwarkanath%20Tagore.](https://er.indianrailways.gov.in/view_section.jsp?fontColor=black&backgroundColor=LIGHTSTEELBLUE&lang=0&id=0,6,443,528,538#:~:text=February%201855%2C%20a%20train%20was,to%20Raniganj%20(194%20Km).&text=During%20the%20middle%20of%20nineteenth,owned%20by%20Sri%20Dwarkanath%20Tagore.)

but steadily, for the demands of capitalist growth of industries, the petrol-engine replaced the steam-boilers completely within 1940.

The main focus of the 1863 Act was to regulate the steam engines of the factories. The special committee constituted by the then Governor General in 1879 proposed to enact the provisions of the 1863 Act in a stringent manner. And from 1880, Government started to implement the provisions of the Act in a stringent manner. This was opposed by the European lobby. Also, a bunch of English-educated Bengalis and other conscious people, with the help of some powerful Europeans in India, stood against those opposing the strict implementation of the 1863 Act. This was the first act of organised movement by Bengalis before Swadeshi movement was started.

The commission set up for the purpose of implementation of the Act limited the amount of emission from the factories. They also started a system whereby the rate of emission was being measured regularly and recorded duly. British India Association recommended these levels for steam-rollers, trains in the city, small workshops etc and they became successful in doing this. Also, a custom of imposing fines for violation of these levels was implemented. But the problem of our age, that is to say, the age of petroleum, is entirely different. Now let us concentrate to that.

SECTION - III

Pollution by Motor Vehicles and Guidelines of WHO

Motor vehicles use fossil fuel generally, and emit particulate materials, oxides of nitrogen, carbon monoxide, organic compounds and lead. As a result, the normal and naturally existing chemical composition of the atmosphere around us gets heavily altered by the addition of these highly toxic chemical species. The levels of air pollutants are rapidly increasing in urban and rural areas in many megacities (urban population greater than 10 million) of the developing world, like Kolkata. The air pollutants thus emitted are detrimental and hazardous to human health. In addition to this, they cause negative impacts on vegetation, animal life, buildings and monuments, weather and climate, and also on the aesthetic quality of the environment.

National Environment Protection Council (NEPC) is a national body that set up the Ambient Air Quality National Environment Protection Measure (AAQ NEPM)⁴ which set national ambient air quality standards. These standards cover 6 common pollutants: particulates, (PM₁₀), ozone, sulphur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide and lead.

WHO estimates that air pollution contributes to approximately 800000 deaths annually⁵. Specifically developing nations are affected; globally as many as two thirds of the deaths and lost life years connected to air pollution occur in Asian countries. To date, estimates of the health effects resulting from exposure to air pollutants in Asia have been done largely on the projection of results from research conducted outside Asia - primarily in Europe and North America. Now let us see the WHO guidelines for the major pollutants⁶:

Air Pollutant	Long-term mean value	Short-term mean value
PM _{2.5}	10µg/m ³ annual	25µg/m ³ 24-hour
PM ₁₀	20µg/m ³ annual	50µg/m ³ 24-hour
O ₃	-	100µg/m ³ 8-hour
NO ₂	40µg/m ³ annual	200µg/m ³ 1-hour
SO ₂	20µg/m ³ 24-hour	500µg/m ³ 10-minute

SECTION – IV

Vehicular Pollution in Kolkata⁷

Concept of vehicular emission

The emission from the vehicles can be categorized as follows:

(a) **Exhaust Emission:** These are emitted through the exhaust pipe when the vehicle is running or is started. This, again, may be of two types:

⁴ https://www.researchgate.net/figure/AAQ-NEPM-air-quality-standards-along-with-maximum-ambient-air-pollutant-concentrations_tbl1_273383224

⁵ https://www.who.int/health-topics/air-pollution#tab=tab_2

⁶ [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ambient-\(outdoor\)-air-quality-and-health](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ambient-(outdoor)-air-quality-and-health)

⁷ Dr. Indrajit Roy Chowdhury, "Scenario of Vehicular Emissions and its Effect on Human Health in Kolkata City", Volume 4 Issue 5, IJHSSI (Online): 2319 – 7722 May, 2015 || PP.01-09

(1) Start up Emission: When the vehicle is started from a rest, start-up emission happens; it may be cold start or hot start. Cold Start is when the vehicle is started suddenly after a long gap of use, whereas, hot start refers to when the vehicle is started without the vehicle getting enough time to cool off after its previous use.

(2) Running Emissions: Emissions during normal running of the vehicle.

(b) Evaporative Emission: These refer to the running losses and hot soak emissions produced from fuel evaporation when an engine is still hot at the end of a trip, and diurnal emissions.

(c) Exhaust Pollutants: The pollutants which are emitted from the exhaust pipe of the automobiles; formed as a result of combustion of the fuel. These pollutants are harmful to the nature and environment.

Let us have a look into the scenario of Kolkata air pollution in a more organised manner:⁸

Pollutants	Description
Nitrogen Oxides (NO)	Road transport contributes to 49% of total NO emission in the city of Kolkata. NO _x is a precursor of ozone formed in the troposphere.
Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂)	Sulphur in diesel contributes to the exhaust particulate matter while in petrol it effects the performance of catalytic converters in engines.
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	Road transport is the principal source of CO in the city of Kolkata.
Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs)	It includes wide range of hydrocarbon oxygenates and halogen-containing species. Petrol vehicles emit more benzene in exhaust than diesel vehicles even if catalytic converters are used. The main source of 1,3 butadiene in the atmosphere is the combustion of petrol and diesel fuels.
Hydro Carbons (HC)	About 10 percent is emitted from automobile exhaust in the city of Kolkata.
Ozone (O₃)	Ozone has a strong diurnal variation with concentration in peak in daytime hours Road traffic is a major contributor to its formation.
Lead (Pb)	The primary source of atmospheric lead in the city of Kolkata is leaded gasoline.
Particulate Matter (PM₁₀)	Transport sectors in Kolkata again emit huge amount of particulate matter in the atmosphere.

⁸ *Ibid*

Major causes of air pollution from automobiles in the city of Kolkata⁹

There are several causes which are responsible for automobile pollution in the city of Kolkata. It includes mainly:

- (a) High emissions from two and three wheelers;
- (b) Using poor-quality fuel like high sulphur, benzene and olefin;
- (c) Adulteration of fuel especially using of *Kata tel* in three wheelers;
- (d) Lack of maintenance of vehicles;
- (e) Large numbers of heavyweight and old petrol vehicles;
- (f) Erratic traffic controls; most of the busy traffic intersecting points in Kolkata have been encroached by pavement dwellers, street hawkers and illegal car-parking, as a result widening space of the road has reduced and thereby results to huge traffic congestion in the city of Kolkata;
- (g) Improper construction of road divider in between two lanes of the road, making inadequate road space which prevent a good mobility of traffic and even unscientific construction of speed breaker reducing traffic speed in the city of Kolkata;
- (h) Improper management of traffic diversion by Kolkata traffic police and problem of traffic signalling system;
- (i) Unscientific construction of flyover, size and weight of the car, inadequate traffic management system;

Effect of vehicular air pollution on human health in the city of Kolkata¹⁰

There are several types of diseases that have been ascribed to the emission of vehicles: (a) Chronic Bronchitis, (b) Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), (c) Lung Cancer, (d) Bronchial Asthma, (e) Allergic Alveolitis, (f) Pulmonary Oedema being prevalent.

⁹ *Ibid*

¹⁰ *Ibid*

Let us tabulate¹¹ the above observation in the following manner:

Carbon Monoxide	Affects cardiovascular system, thus creating cardio-vascular diseases symptoms, particularly angina; affects nervous system impairing physical co-ordination, vision and judgment, creating nausea and headaches, reducing productivity and increasing personal discomfort.
Nitrogen Oxides	Increased susceptibility to infections, pulmonary diseases, impairment of lung function and eye, nose and throat irritations.
Sulphur di-oxide	Affect lung function adversely.
SPM & RPM	Fine particulate matter may be toxic in itself or may carry toxic trace substance, and can alter the immune system. Fine particulates penetrate deep into the respiratory system, irritating lung tissue and causing long term disorders.
Benzene	Both toxic and carcinogenic excessive incidence of leukaemia (blood cancer) in high exposures area.
Lead	Impairs liver and kidney causes brain damage in children resulting in lower I.Q., hyperactivity and reduce ability to concentrate.

Ward-wise division of major traffic crossings in the city of Kolkata

If we have to get a very clear picture of the air pollutants that are emitted into the atmosphere of Kolkata city, we must look into the details of the important traffic crossings of the city and prepare a ward wise data sheet¹² for the entire city:

Borough	Wards	Crossing	Zone	Description
II	11	Shyambazar five point	I	North
III	13	Ultadanga	I	North
IV	44, 50, 45, 27	MG Road, Moulali, BBD Bag, Maniktala	I & V	North & Central
VI	46	Esplanade	V	Central
VII	64, 67 66	Park Circus, Picnic Garden, Science City Connector	V & III	Central & East
VIII	86, 84, 72, 69	Gariahat, Rashbehari, Hazra, Ballygaunge Phanri	II	South
IX	77	Khidderpore	IV	West
X	100, 94	Garia, Tollygaunge Phanri	II	South
XI	102	Jadavpur	II	South
XIII & XIV	116	Behala	IV	West
XV	137	Garden Reach	IV	West

¹¹ *Ibid*

¹² *Ibid*

SECTION – V

Vehicular Air Pollution: Regulations, Standards and Bodies

Statutory Provisions regarding Vehicular Air Pollution:

The statutes, rules and regulations that control the issue of vehicular air pollution in Kolkata as well as India, can be briefly summarised as:

1. *Essential Commodities Act, 1955*
2. *The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981¹³*
3. *The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Rules, 1982¹⁴*
4. *The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986¹⁵*
5. *The Environment (Protection) Rules, 1986¹⁶*
6. *Motor Vehicles Act, 1988¹⁷*
7. *Motor Vehicles Rules, 1989¹⁸*
8. *West Bengal Motor Vehicles Rules, 1989¹⁹*
9. *The Petroleum and Natural Gas Rules (PNGR), 2002*
10. *Petroleum and Natural Gas Regulatory Board Act, 2006*
11. *National Ambient Air Quality Standards, 2009²⁰*
12. *National Green Tribunal Act, 2010²¹*
13. *Constitution of India, Articles 48A, 51A and Art. 21*
14. *National Auto Policy*
15. *Automotive Mission Plan 2026*

The *Essential Commodities Act, 1955* ensures that all essential commodities, including petroleum products, are easily available to the public and meet government

¹³ No.14 of 1981, [29/3/1981]

¹⁴ GSR 712(E), dated 18th. November, 1982

¹⁵ No.29 of 1986, [23/5/1986]

¹⁶ S.O. 844(E), dated 19.11.1986, published in the Gazette of India, Ext., Part 2., Section 3(i), dated 19.11.1986

¹⁷ 1st July, 1989, vide notification No. S.O. 368(E), dated 22nd May, 1989

¹⁸ Inserted by GSR 933(E) dt. 28-10-1989

¹⁹ Introduced vide Notification No. TS-889, dated 16.12.1989, Transport Department, Government of West Bengal

²⁰ New Delhi, the 18th November, 2009 No..B-29016/20/90/PCI-L (CPCB)

²¹ No.19 of 2010 [2/6/2010]

standards. It also calls for fines, imprisonment up to one year, and forfeiture of the right to do business for those who violate the act.

The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981 gives state pollution control boards the right to prohibit the production or burning of any fuel that leads to air pollution. This Act applies to the whole of India and is a comprehensive legislation, enacted for the purpose of controlling the air pollution due to various reasons and sources. If we trace the history of this legislation, we would see that Sweden first suggested to the United Nations that there should be a global conference to discuss so as to prevent the degradation of natural resources. Thereafter the General Assembly Resolution No 2398²² was passed in the UN Conference on the Human Environment held in Stockholm in June 1972. In this conference it was decided that the countries would undertake steps to preserve natural resources that also includes air. Accordingly, the Indian government enacted specific laws under Article 253 of the Constitution of India for the preservation of natural resources and the law enacted for air preservation was *The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981*.

Actually, this was the first legislation whereby the standardised definition of pollution was given for the first time in its Sec 2(a), and in Sec. 2(b) the definition of air pollution was given.

But perhaps the most important contribution of this Act to the Indian environmental legislations is the set-up of the two statutory bodies – The Central Pollution Control Board u/s 2(g) and The State Pollution Control Boards u/s 2(o). Thereby Sections 3 and 4 state the composition of the Boards.

Thereafter in Sec 16, the Functions of the Central Board is given in a very velar manner, a simple reading of which reveals the fact it has wide ambit of powers across the country to combat air pollution, including vehicular pollution. Also, it has been given the power to lay down the standards for the quality of air.

Section 17 lays down the functions of the State Pollution Control Board amongst which it is empowered to lay down standards for the emission of air pollutants into the atmosphere from automobiles.

Section 20 states that the State Government may, after consulting the State Pollution Control Board, issue instructions to the competent authority responsible for

²² <https://research.un.org/en/docs/ga/quick/regular/23>

the registration of vehicles under the MV Act, and such authority shall be bound to follow these instructions.

The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 does not specifically mention fuels, but does authorize the central and the state governments to regulate activities that can harm the environment, under which the burning of fossil fuels could be included. This was passed with the object to implement the decisions which were made at the UN Conference on the Human Environment held at Stockholm in June 1972, like creation of authority for government protection, coordinating the activities of various regulating agencies which is done under the existing law etc. It was also enacted for providing deterrent punishment to those who violate norms and endanger the health and well-being of citizens through pollution.

While the Air Act, 1981 and Environment Act, 1986 specifically mention The Central Pollution Control Board and State Pollution Control Board's roles in setting up environmental standards, it is ultimately the Ministry of Road Transport and Highways (MoRTH) who is responsible for enforcing compliance with India's vehicular emission standards.

While the MoRTH sets norms for in-use emission standards, individual states and municipalities are responsible for enforcing them. Another set of responsibility lies with the national agencies that carry out type approval and COP testing. These agencies are under the management of various other ministries rather than the MoRTH. For example, two such agencies, the Automotive Research Association of India (ARAI) and the International Centre for Automotive Technology (ICAT), the primary passenger vehicle testing agencies, are managed by the Ministry of Heavy Industries & Public Enterprises (MoHIPE).

The MV Act, 1988 established vehicular emission standards and authorized the central government and state governments to further regulate and enforce them.

The Petroleum and Natural Gas Rules (PNGR), 2002 list specific guidelines to be followed for the importation and/or refinement of fuel in India, and the transport of fuel within the country.

The Petroleum and Natural Gas Regulatory Board Act, 2006 constituted the Petroleum and Natural Gas Regulatory Board (PNGRB) and is responsible for ensuring fuel quality standards, from import or production through retail sales. PNGRB is charged with ensuring that the PNGR are followed. The PNGRB is also authorized to resolve all disputes that may arise among producers, transporters, retailers, and

consumers over fuel related issues and has legal authority to enforce fuel quality standards at retail outlets.

The *West Bengal Motor Vehicles Rules 1989* provides for strict compliance with the *CMV Act* and prescribing penalties for the violation of the same. As per the website data of West Bengal Traffic Police²³, accessed on 29.04.2021 at 21:15 hrs, it is found that the offence named Violation of Standards Prescribed for Road Safety, control of Noise & Air Pollution u/s 190(2) attracts a first-time penalty of Rs. 1500/-, Rs. 2000/- for the second offence and Rs. 2000/- for the third offence. All this is connected with the production of on demand PUC, the failure of which attracts the said penalties. Under Rule 115(2) of the *Central Motor Vehicles Act, 1989*, the pollution standards or emission levels are fixed for motor vehicles in India. The government revises the emission levels of vehicles on a regular basis to keep the pollution levels in the country under control.

National Green Tribunal was established in 2010 which was under the *National Green Tribunal Act, 2010*. It is the most important adjudicatory body regarding environmental pollution. It was constituted on 18.10.2010²⁴ for effective and expeditious disposal of matters relating to environmental protection and conservation of forests and other natural resources including enforcement of any legal right and giving relief and compensation for damages to persons and property and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto. It is a specialized body equipped with the necessary expertise to handle environmental disputes involving multi-disciplinary issues. The Tribunal is not bound by the procedure laid down under the Code of Civil Procedure, 1908, but is guided by principles of natural justice.

The Tribunal's dedicated jurisdiction in environmental matters provides a speedy environmental justice and helps reduce the burden of litigation in the higher courts. The Tribunal is mandated to make and endeavour for disposal of applications or appeals finally within 6 months of filing of the same.

The draft of *National Auto Policy 2018* suggests to adopt a long-term roadmap to decide emission standards after BS-VI era and harmonize emission standards with global benchmarks by 2028. It also recommends *Corporate Average Fuel Economy (CAFE)* standards by 2025.

²³ <https://www.wbtrafficpolice.com/offences-and-penalties.php>

²⁴ <https://greentribunal.gov.in/about-us>

The policy advocates the harmonization of standards over the next 5 years and evaluates accession to the UNECE WP.29 1958 agreement within the same period. It also suggests upgrading facilities and developing expertise at NATRiP, a testing agency, as per requirements for testing according to the *Bharat New Vehicle Safety Assessment Program (BNVSAP)*. The policy also supports implementation of a vehicle scrapping policy - *Voluntary Vehicle Modernization Program (V-VMP)*.²⁵

Automotive Mission Plan 2026 (AMP 2026) has been finalized jointly by the Government of India and the Indian Automotive Industry. The AMP 2026 is focused on bringing the Indian Automotive Industry within the top three in the world for engineering, manufacturing and exports of vehicles & components; with the goal of growing in value to make up 12% of India's GDP and generate an additional 65 million jobs. AMP will contribute to the “Make in India” and the “Skill India” programs. It also aims for a five-fold increase in the export of vehicles and a 7.5-fold increase in the export of components.

A brief time line of implementation of policy and review can be found below:

Suggested emission roadmap after BS-VI

Segment	Stage	Year	Engine Type	Test Cycle	CO	HC	NMHC	NOx	HC + NOx	PM
					g/km for PV & 2W; g/kw-h for CV					
Passenger Vehicles	BS VI	2020	PI	IDC	1	0.1	-	0.06	-	0.0045
	CI		IDC	0.5	-	-	0.08	0.17	0.0045	
	Post BS VI	2028	PI	WLTP + RDE	0.5	0.05	-	0.02	-	0.002
Commercial Vehicles	BS VI	2020	CI	WHSC	1.5	0.13	-	0.4	-	0.01
			CI	WHTC	4	0.16	-	0.46	-	0.01
	Post BS VI	2028	-	WHSC	1.5	0.13	-	0.27	-	0.01
			-	WHTC	4	0.16	-	0.27	-	0.01
Two-Wheelers	BS VI	2020	PI	WMTC	1	0.1	-	0.06	-	0.0045
	CI		WMTC	0.5	0.1	-	0.09	-	0.0045	
	Post BS VI	2028	PI	WMTC	0.5	-	0.068	0.06	-	0.0045
Three-Wheelers	BS VI	2020	PI	IDC	0.44	-	-	0.13	0.435	-
			CI	IDC	0.22	-	-	0.16	0.2	0.025
	Post BS VI	2028	PI	IDC	1	-	0.068	0.06	-	0.0045
			CI	IDC	0.5	-	0.068	0.06	-	0.0045

Announced
Proposed
XX – Changed compared to BS VI XX – No change from BS VI

²⁵ https://www.marklines.com/en/report_all/rep1805_201901#report_area_1

Regulatory Agencies regarding Vehicular Pollution

Other than the statutory bodies mentioned above, following are some regulatory agencies:

1. *Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS)*
2. *Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change*
3. *Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas*
4. *Ministry of Road Transportation and Highways*

SECTION – VI

Vehicular Air Pollution: Judicial Pronouncements

There are ample case laws regarding vehicular air pollution in Kolkata. We will not only be discussing the cases related and limited to Kolkata, but also cases that have wide implications regarding the controlling and mitigating the city air pollution resulting from vehicular emissions. Let us remember the fact that air pollution is also caused by the emissions from various industries, forest fires and several other sources. But here we are concerned with the vehicular air pollution only. Now let us consider the following:

1. *M.C. Mehta vs Union of India And Ors*²⁶

M.C Mehta being a public-spirited citizen, has a host of case laws registered against his name for the protection of environment. Let us discuss a summary of all those briefly.

In a case dated 1991, discussions regarding the following matter were undertaken: lead free petrol was introduced in four metropolitan cities in 1995. All cars manufactured after 1995 were fitted with catalytic convertors to reduce emissions. CNG outlets had been set up to provide CNG to vehicles. A committee was set up to look into the problem of Vehicular Pollution in Delhi and to find methods to arrest pollution. The committee was setup with the following objectives –

²⁶ *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India* [(1998) 6 SCC 60]
M.C. Mehta v. Union of India [(1998) 6 SCC 63]
M.C. Mehta v. Union of India [(1999) 6 SCC 12]
M.C. Mehta v. Union of India [(2002) 10 SCC 191]

- i. To make an assessment of the technologies available for vehicular pollution control in the world;
- ii. To make an assessment of the current status of technology available in India for controlling vehicular pollution;
- iii. To look at the low-cost alternatives for operating vehicles at reduced pollution levels in the metropolitan cities of India.
- iv. To examine the feasibility of measures to reduce/eliminate pollution from motor vehicles both on short term and long-term basis and make appropriate recommendations in this regard;
- v. To make specific recommendations on the administrative/legal regulations required for implementing the recommendations in (iii) above.

In another matter the chief question asked was whether the accumulated stock of BS-III compliant vehicles manufactured on or before 31-3-2017 could be sold and registered after 1-4-2017, and Whether the stock of BS-III compliant vehicles manufactured on or before 31-3-2017 can be sold from 1-4-2017 or not. The court pronounced that it is an established legal principle that the right to life includes the right to a decent environment. It includes within its scope the right of a citizen to live in a clean environment. It also re-iterated that various directions have been issued to ensure a clean environment and reduce pollution. The right to clean environment is a fundamental right envisaged under article 21. The right to live in a smoke-free and pollution-free environment derives from the “quality” of life, which is an inherent part of Article 21 of the Constitution. The right to live with human dignity becomes illusory in the absence of a healthy environment. The right to life not only means leading a dignified life but also includes within its scope the right to lead a healthy and solid life in a clean and pollution-free atmosphere. These rights are not absolute and must coexist with sustainable development. And therefore, if there is a conflict between health and wealth; health will have to take priority. The broader public interest has to overcome the much smaller pecuniary interest of the industry, in this case, the automobile industry, especially when there are all means to introduce the cleanest technology. In its opinion, Sub-Rule 21 of Rule 115 is very vague and does not speak of vehicle sales. It only mentions the registration of vehicles and allows the registration of vehicles that comply with BS-IV standards until 30.06.2020 and in the case of categories M and N, until 30.09.2020. This rule violates Article 21 of the Constitution. Extend the time for vehicle registration beyond 31.03.2020 and should be read accordingly. The Apex

Court finally stated that when it comes to the health of millions of people, the notification related to commercial activities should not be interpreted literally. One has to give purposive interpretation to the notifications, especially to those that deal with public health problems and even more, when the health of not only citizens today but also citizens in the future is involved. Hence, no motor vehicle conforming to the emission standard Bharat Stage IV shall be sold or registered in the entire country with effect from 01.04.2020.

While delivering the judgement, the Hon'ble Court observed that SIAM has been investigating that the change to BS-VI compatible vehicles are a long process that requires major changes in technology; the same manufacturers are selling and exporting BS-VI compatible vehicles to Europe and other countries. It was of the opinion that some of the manufacturers are not willing to meet the deadline of 03.31.2020 not because they do not have the technology, but because the use of technology will lead to an increase in the cost of vehicles that can lead to the reduction of vehicle sales and, ultimately, of their profits. The court was of the view that when BS-VI and BS-IV fuels are compared there is a massive improvement in environmental terms. The court was of the view that it makes no economic sense to have more polluting vehicles on the roads. The effect of pollution on the environment and health is so huge that it cannot be compensated in the marginal extra profits that the manufacturers might -make. The amount spent on countering the ills of pollution such as polluted air damaged lungs and the cost of healthcare far outweigh the profits earned. There is enough time for manufacturers to switch to the new system and, therefore, we see no reason why they should be given a window of three or six months for the sale of accumulated vehicles. The court was of the opinion that purposive interpretation should be given to notifications, especially those dealing with public health problems, and even more so when it comes to the health of not only current citizens but also citizens in the future.

2. *Subhas Dutta vs State of West Bengal & ors.*

As like MC Mehta, Subhas Dutta is also a public-spirited citizen concerned about various aspects of environmental pollution. It is the case of him due to which the West Bengal Pollution Control Board had submitted reports that were alarming revealing the air quality of Kolkata to be highly polluted as it was stated to be not only higher than the day time but also five to six times in excess of the safe limit. In this matter the petitioner was concerned particularly with the magnitude of auto-emission in the city

which, as per him, is the major contributor to pollution requiring urgent attention. In a previous matter of the same petitioner, the Hon'ble High Court directed:

- a) Phasing out of old vehicle;
- b) Strict compliance of the Bharat Stage norms;
- c) Introduction of green-fuel;
- d) No. PUC, no fuel,
- e) Strengthening the system of inspection, maintenance and certification of vehicles;
- f) Formation of High-Power Monitoring Committee to control and regulate pollution in the KMC areas;
- g) Effective use of Remote Sensing Device (RSD) etc.

The causes for the high level of pollution in the city of Kolkata are the lack of clean fuel, old vehicles plying in the city which is stated to constitute 54% of the total number, slow movement of traffic, high density of vehicles and deficient method in checking and control of emission. As directed by the Hon'ble High Court, the State Government procured one Remote Sensing Device (RSD) in the month of November, 2009, an instrument which instantly measures emissions with accuracy. In an apparent conflict of action, the State Government, in a meeting held on 02.07.2010, took a decision to relax even the Pollution Under Control (PUC) limits by resolving as follows:

1. Vehicles detected by the RSD with the pollution level not exceeding 20% of the permissible level should not be penalised for the present.
2. Report on pollution of vehicles detected by RSD in respect of vehicles plying within one year from the date of its first registration should be ignored and should not be penalised for the present.
3. In case a single vehicle is detected more than once by the RSD in a single calendar month, penalty is to be realised against a single case only once in a month and others be ignored.
4. In case a single vehicle is detected more than once by the RSD in consecutive 3 (three) calendar months, careful examination of the vehicle to ascertain the emission level within the prescribed limit by the Officer of M.V. Department is to be done in addition to imposition of penalty as usual. For repeated detection of any vehicles by the RSD in consecutive 3 (three) months, the Registering Authority may also take action to suspend registration of the vehicle etc. in accordance with prescribed Acts & Rules. The vehicle may also be tested by the

same RSD machine, if necessary. Even the only RSD in operation was stopped from 18th November, 2014 thereby adding to the woes of the city.

On 17th November, 2014, upon hearing the Applicant, NGT issued notices upon the competent authorities on the air pollution arising out of auto emission during both the day and night hours in Kolkata, Howrah, North and South 24 Parganas on the following grounds:

1. Air quality index in Kolkata remains as very poor next to Delhi only in most of the time. The situation becomes worse during winter due to meteorological factors.
2. The SPM level at B.T. Road, Shyambazar, Ultadanga & Moulali is close to three times of the same limit.
3. A surge in construction contributes significantly to air pollution, which is a significant contribution to SPM. Though the government and the private firms are spending crores of rupees on projects, they do not spend a fraction needed to control dust.
4. A study conducted by *Kala Gopala Krishnan* in 1997 reveals 50% of pollution to automobiles and 48% to industry and rest to other activities. But subsequently the situation has changed with a boom in construction and an explosion in plying of vehicles.
5. A study conducted by IIT, Kanpur reveals that the top contributor of PM₁₀ (56%) and PM_{2.5}(38%) in Delhi is road dust. Fuel burning contribution to PM_{2.5} is 20% and for SPM it is 9%. The study also shows that the percentage contribution of various sources like road dust, industrial point sources, domestic fuel burning, vehicles and other sources to PM₁₀ & PM_{2.5} in ambient air.
6. Air monitoring data of American consulate reveal that Kolkata Air is worse than Delhi with respect to PM_{2.5} which is one of the most dangerous elements in auto emission.
7. A study by Chittaranjan National Cancer Research Institute shows how people of Kolkata are exposed to dangerous level of air pollutants because of high density of vehicular pollution on a limited road space of 6% compared to 26% road space in Delhi. The open space in Kolkata is only 1% for which emission in the city stays for a longer period. The low average speed of vehicles in Kolkata due to heavy traffic in limited space leads to poor combustion of fuel and more pollution. Thus, with the present Business as Usual attitude of the

stakeholders, time is not far when Kolkata will be listed as worst polluted city in the world with large proportion of children and elderly people suffering from lung related diseases and even cancer. Therefore, it is high time that judiciary intervenes to stabilise and reduce the pollution load in the ambient air which may require some drastic step at the cost of comfort of some people for whom a large section of poor people, whose contribution to pollution is negligible, also suffer.

8. In Kolkata nearly 65% of all vehicles and 99% of commercial vehicles are diesel run which emit toxic carcinogens. Kolkata has earned the notoriety as diesel capital of India. The report also discusses the mobility crisis as 65% of the arterial roads in Kolkata are congested. Interestingly the majority of Kolkata citizens who experience the air pollution problem want a change. Many suggestions have been made in each aspect to combat the air pollution level. As there is no recent scientific data available on contribution of various sources to PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and Nitrogen Dioxide level of ambient air in the twin cities, the State Pollution Control Board shall engage national level agencies to collect and generate data on contribution of various sources of pollution at important areas in both the city in order to formulate strategy to combat air pollution. Compliance report on engagement of agency to undertake the work be filed within four weeks & report of agencies within three months. The air quality of Kolkata city (on the basis of 11 monitoring stations) exceeds long term NAAQS 2009 (Annual average of 104 observations) for 3 major parameters i.e., PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂ for all the stations.
9. Analysis of air quality data reveals that while the night time concentrations in Kolkata and Howrah are higher than the day time concentration in winter time, the phenomena is reserved during the summer months. This happens due to change in weather conditions.
10. The ambient air quality network of 13 stations (including Kolkata and Howrah) currently operated by the WBPCB needs augmentation. Besides automobile emission, other sources like road dust and construction activities, burning of municipal wastes and industrial wastes including plastics, operation of DG sets and industrial emissions etc. are also contributing to the deterioration of air quality of these twin cities. Therefore, WBPCB should initiate a source

apportionment study to assess the contribution from different emission sources in the air in Kolkata and.

11. On the basis of the distribution of traffic, the committee requested the WBPCB to initiate air quality monitoring at 5/6 more stations in Kolkata city. The WBPCB has initiated air quality monitoring in 19 stations in Kolkata from January 2016.
12. PM_{2.5} is considered to be the worst air polluter. WBPCB measured this parameter at two stations till 2015, and, considering the traffic density and migration profile, has increased two more stations in Kolkata. Further to this the two CAAQM stations at Victoria and RBU will have PM_{2.5} installation by this year and the new stations at Science City, BITM and Sector V in Kolkata and Ramakrishna Mission University, Belur and Padmapukur Water Works in Howrah will have similar installations.
13. The final Report of the Expert Committee was submitted on 24th February, 2016. We record our appreciation of the fact that the Committee has dealt with the matter in meticulous detail in preparing the report which would serve as a data base for the concerned authorities, particularly the Departments of Transport and Environment as well the WBPCB, in dealing with matters associated with ambient air in the city of Kolkata.

SECTION – VII

Policy and Guidelines to reduce Vehicular Air Pollution in the city of Kolkata

Considering the abovementioned landmark judgements of Calcutta High Court and the Eastern Bench of the NGT, keeping in mind the recommendations of the *Bhure Lal Committee* constituted by order of the Hon'ble Supreme Court dated 07.01.1998, following are a brief summary:

1. That about 50000 heavily loaded goods carrying vehicles enter into the city during night hours. There are no checks and control on their emissions. It is required to have emission test-centres and weighment arrangements at all the

entry points to the State of West Bengal. Police should check the PUC certificate of all lorries at night hours.

2. That most of the road repairing in the cities are being done through primitive process by burning firewood/tyre etc. In Delhi even Hot-mixing-machines are not allowed to operate. In our cities Micro-Surfacing System of road repairing/making needs to be introduced which is cost-effective, fast and environment-friendly.
3. That the road space in Kolkata is less than 5%, street vendors occupy a sizeable portion of footpaths and roads, causing less flow of traffic. *National Policy on Street Vendors, 2009* and earmarking of Vending Zones have not been done in West Bengal as yet. Such policy should be framed and followed strictly at the earliest.
4. The traffic signal synchronization will substantially improve the movement of vehicles. There have been repetitive directions by the High Court at Calcutta to synchronize all traffic signals surrounding the Victoria Memorial Hall, which is yet to be done. At least for CBD there should be total synchronization of traffic signals.
5. That 90% of the public transport/goods carrying vehicles operate by diesel in Kolkata. Phasing out of such polluting vehicles should be initiated. Till such time a cess may be imposed on diesel and the collected money can be utilised for improving the environmental health of the city.
6. That none of the state-run public transport vehicles and highly polluting waste carrying vehicles of the Municipal Corporations hold any PUC. Those vehicles should also be brought under strict PUC umbrella.
7. That there should be marking of parking spaces at different areas of the city and no parking should be allowed within the CBD.
8. That Kolkata is having several wholesale markets and godowns well within the CBD. Once the Government took a decision to relocate those markets but that has not yet done. Shifting of such markets should be initiated.
9. That Kolkata should also go for allowing operations of odd and even number of vehicles on alternate day.
10. That new permits are issued for stage carriage every now and then without caring for the capacity of the roads. All such new permits are given for routes through CBD. This practice causes terrible traffic congestions. It is, therefore,

extremely urgent that no new permits be given through CBD and without making any study on road capacity.

11. That no slow-moving carriers like rickshaw/van etc should be allowed to operate from 8 AM to 8 PM in the CBD of the city. The battery-operated rickshaw, called as TOTO, should be disallowed to operate within the city limits.
12. That other relevant aspects like quality of fuel (*Kanta Tel*), installation of air-filters in schools/colleges, introduction of BS V/IV, staggering of office hours, stopping of auto-rickshaws as stage carriage, better traffic management, improving surface road-conditions, better public transport system, introduction of cycle-way and walk-way in Salt Lake City and New Town, may be considered.

Recommendations for the WBPCB

A. Augmentation of air monitoring network

1. The WBPCB has already made all semi-automatic air monitoring stations functional with effect from 01.01.2016, which were in operation till 2011. These monitoring stations operate in such a way that the air quality of Kolkata is being monitored every day. However, the ambient air quality network of twenty-four (24) stations (in Kolkata and Howrah) currently operated by the WBPCB needs further augmentation through installation of five (5) additional continuous air monitoring stations near Science City, Ballygunge Phanri and Sector-V, Bidhannagar in Kolkata and at Ramakrishna Mission University, Belur and Padmapukur Water Works in Howrah.
2. The WBPCB should make arrangements for continuous monitoring of PM_{2.5} at the existing automatic air monitoring stations at Victoria Memorial Hall and Rabindra Bharati University and also at the additional five (5) recommended stations as mentioned above. Therefore, PM_{2.5} which was monitored in two (2) stations only in Kolkata, should be monitored in nine (9) stations.
3. Since sources like road dust, construction activities, burning of municipal wastes and industrial wastes (including plastics), operation of DG sets and industrial emissions etc. are also contributing to the deterioration of air quality of these twin cities, the WBPCB should initiate a Source Apportionment Study to collect and generate data on contribution of various sources of pollution at

important areas in Kolkata in order to formulate strategy to combat air pollution. This study may be conducted by a national level agency, which has the expertise and experience in conducting such studies.

4. Long-term Air Quality Management Plan for Kolkata City may be evolved on the basis of the results of Source Apportionment Study to be carried out by WBPCB.
5. The Air Quality Index (AQI) is an important first step for improving air quality in urban areas as it leads to improvement in public awareness on local pollution levels and associated health advisories. For example, the AQI identifies sensitive populations that should take special precaution including people with asthma, lung ailments and heart disease. It also alerts people to make daily lifestyle adjustments on high severity days. Accordingly, to protect citizens from air pollution, the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of India recently launched a National Air Quality Index (AQI) alert system for major cities that notifies the public about air pollution levels and associated health risks. The WBPCB should explore the possibility to integrate Kolkata and Howrah twin city with National AQI alert system.
6. The WBPCB along with Kolkata Municipal Corporation (KMC) and Howrah Municipal Corporation (HMC) should display air quality data in electronic display boards at strategic locations in Kolkata and Howrah.

B. Traffic management

1. Phasing out/scrapping of commercial vehicles that are more than 15 years old.
2. Traffic re-engineering to remove congestion from densely populated/most frequented road stretches.
3. Traffic signals may be replaced with circular round about for removal of congestion from densely populated/most frequented road stretches.
4. Underpasses may be constructed in major crossings where large scale cross over of pedestrian takes place.
5. Strict enforcement of possession of valid PUC Certificate in all the vehicles plying within Kolkata and Howrah city and imposition of penalty for noncompliance of the same.
6. Operationalisation of E-Rickshaws and E-Carts as the mode of transport for last mile connectivity.

7. Strict enforcement of No Parking Rules and compounding of offences committed.
8. Construction of multi-layered or underground car parking space.
9. KMC and HMC should insist on either underground or multitier parking arrangement within the premises while sanctioning building plans for Malls etc.
10. Construction of pavements for all city streets to increase space for smooth traffic movement.
11. Provision of cycling and walk ways throughout the two cities.

C. Streamlining efficiency of Auto Emission Testing Centres

1. Number and operational aspects of the AETCs need to be relooked by the State Transport Department enhancement/betterment.
 2. AETCs should be connected to a centralized server for better monitoring and enforcement.
 3. Following the order of the Honble Tribunal dated 19 January 2016, the WBPCB has already conducted surprise raids in February 2016. Surprise inspection of the AETCs to check the calibration of the emission testing equipment and proper functioning of the AETCs, should be continued. Strict penalties to be imposed on AETCs for violation under the relevant Acts and Rules by the authority.
- D. Other recommendations**
4. Open burning of coal and wood in Kolkata and Howrah should be stopped.
 5. Strict implementation of direction issued by Department of Environment, Govt. of West Bengal vide no. EN/3170/T-IV-7/001/2009 dated 10 December 2009 (Annexure-C) by the concerned Municipal Authorities (KMC and HMC) and all concerned Government Departments for controlling air pollution.
 6. Complete banning of open burning of solid waste including dry leaves in the city areas.
 7. Plantation of new leafy saplings in the available space in different parts of the twin cities to mitigate the level of air pollution.
 8. Sprinkling of water daily at important traffic junctions of the twin cities of Kolkata and Howrah during the peak winter months (October to February) by Kolkata Municipal Corporation and Howrah Municipal Corporation to mitigate suspension of particulate matters to the air.
 9. Air pollution problem of Kolkata has become complex due to multiplicity and complexity of air polluting sources (e.g. industries, automobiles, generator sets,

domestic fuel burning, road side dusts, construction activities, etc.).The proposed Source Apportionment Study, which would be primarily based on measurements and tracking down the sources through receptor modelling, would help in identifying the sources and extent of their contribution in deteriorating the air quality of city of Kolkata. Once results of Source Apportionment Study are available, a cost- effective integrated approach for managing air quality would be evolved including (a) identification of emission sources; (b) assessment of extent of contribution of these sources on ambient environment; (c) prioritizing the sources that need to be tackled; (d) evaluate various options for controlling the sources with regard to feasibility and economic viability; and (e) formulation and implementation of most appropriate action plans for managing air quality of Kolkata.

SECTION – VIII

Data Analysis

Introduction

The key element in conducting an empirical study is sampling for the purpose of data collection. At first the researcher designs his study, and then uses various tolls for the collection of data through sampling. For a study which involves social outreach, it is mandatory that a sample be chosen by the researcher and tolls administered to them. A sample is a portion of people drawn from a larger population. It will be representative of the population only if it has same basic characteristics of the population from which it is drawn. Our concern in sampling is not about what types of units will be interviewed but with how many units of what particular description and by what method should be chosen (Singleton and Straits, 199:134).

Due to the prevailing pandemic situation, all the data were collected through questionnaire format using google form. The respective responses are depicted in graphical form in this section for a ready understanding.

We know that questionnaire is a structured set of questions. It is used as a tool when we need ease in administration. According to Black and Champion, 1976:379, in deciding whether questionnaire is an appropriate tool for data collection, following four

aspects must be borne in mind: 1) identify situations for which questions are best suited, 2) Discuss advantages and disadvantages of a questionnaire as a research tool of data collection, 3) Delineate dimensions to be associated with questionnaire construction, 4) differentiate between several types of questionnaires.

For the purpose of the present empirical study, topic-based questions were used in the structured questionnaire for recording the responses of the target interviewee. The method of administration was electronic – through a link of google form. No specific target patterns were chosen for the interviewee, as can be seen from Table 1. The total number of questions used were twenty (20). All the questions used for recording responses were of close-ended type. There are certain advantages of administering close-ended questions. These are as follows: 1) These provide a greater uniformity of responses, 2) It is very easy to code, score and process standard answers which saves time and energy, 3) The respondent has not to use much brain as he is often clear and certain about the meaning of the question, 4) Little time is taken to complete the questionnaire, 5) Answers can be compared from person to person, 6) Irrelevant responses are not at all received and the answers are relatively complete, 7) Response rate is high.

There are certain advantages of using questionnaire as a tool for data collection: 1) lower costing, 2) time saving, 3) accessibility to widespread respondents, 4) no interviewer's bias, 5) greater anonymity, 6) respondents' convenience, 7) standardised wordings, 8) no variation

Data Collection and Graphical Representation

Table 2: Age Group Composition of interviewee

Table 3: Gender Composition of interviewee

Data Analysis for the Current Study

In the present set of data that were obtained by the researcher, we can see that a total twenty-three (23) tables have been shown amongst which the first three are the details of the interviewee and the rest are the questions. The questions used were easy to respond, anonymous and direct in nature. No previous knowledge of the respondents was necessary except for a few questions. The questionnaire was formed with a view to test the general consciousness and knowledge of the sample group chosen. As the number of respondents is 125, we can safely infer that this constitutes a large enough cohort for the study.

From **Table 1**, it is seen that students constitute a large fraction of this study. Hence the responses recorded represent society as whole since the students will populate various sectors and professions of society in future and generally it is seen that

they are relatively unbiased in forming their opinion compared to the more mature section of the society.

Table 2 confirms Table 1. As students form a larger section of the study, hence the age group 18-25 constitute the majority age group of this study.

In this male-dominated society, an exception is **Table 3**, where women are majority. A fact about google form is they are administered easily and can reach a large number of samples. Among those it is seen that women have participated in a comparatively large number than the males. This may be due to the anonymous nature of the questions administered. Women give priority to their privacy above all and hence in responding to the questionnaire, they may have felt safe as no personal data was collected at all.

It is a fact that not all people who own vehicle of any kind know all the relevant laws and details of authorities related to motor vehicle administration system. Through **Table 4, Question 1**, the researcher intended to have a picture of the composition of the target sample who own and/or possess vehicles of any kind that cause pollution, and who do not.

Pollution in a city like Kolkata is not only caused by vehicular emission, but also from various other sources. Hence, **Question 2** was framed to assess the opinion of the sample population about the major contributor to the air pollution in city of Kolkata. From the response pattern it is found that 89% of the respondents believe and/or are of opinion that the major cause of air pollution in city of Kolkata is vehicular exhaust. This is shown in **Table 5**.

We know very well that the basic and entry-level control system of vehicular pollution starts from the pollution clearance certificate. Hence **Question 3** was framed to assess the opinion of the test sample population about their knowledge and belief in pollution clearance certificate of vehicles. **Table 6** shows that 54% of the total respondents hold the opinion that if the pollution clearance certificate is issued after proper examination of the vehicle, the air pollution due to vehicular emission can be effectively controlled. Alternatively, we can say from this table that the larger portion of people believe that the pollution clearance certificate of the vehicles is not issued in a proper manner.

Table 7 contains general question (**Question 4**) to verify whether the test population are aware of the various pollution controlling mechanisms installed in a vehicle, namely Bharat Standard. From the responses it is shown that 57% of the test

population know that a pollution controlling mechanism named Bharat Standard is installed in vehicles and they have acronyms like BS IV, BS VI etc.

In **Table 8** a basic question was asked to verify the knowledge and opinion of the test population about the cost of minimising pollution from vehicular exhaust. From the responses of **Question 5**, it is shown that a majority of people believe that minimising pollution from vehicular exhaust does not require a high cost.

Since the city in our study is Kolkata, we happen to have a great heritage of our city, namely tram, which is a pollution-less vehicle. **Table 9** depicts the opinion of the people engaged for sample collection through **Question 6**, weather increasing the use of tram can be an effective and feasible measure to reduce vehicular pollution in a city like Kolkata. A large part of the respondents has answered this question in positive. This shows that people are aware about the burning of fossil fuel in vehicles and the resulting pollution. Since trams do not use any kind of fossil fuels, people prefer this vehicle to the others for minimising the pollution due to vehicular emission in Kolkata city.

Question 7 shown in **Table 10** records the opinion of the test sample about the fuel used in future vehicles - whether it is CNG or hydrogen gas or electricity. From the responses it is seen that 61% of the respondents have voted in favour of hybrid vehicles using both fuel and electricity as power source. This shows the concern of the people who constitute middle-class section of the society about the future of city commute.

We know that pollution created by vehicular emission has several devastating effects. **Question 8** was framed to assess the opinion of the test sample about the most devastating of these. This is shown in **Table 11**. From the responses it is well established that people are squarely divided between two responses, namely, poor air quality (44%) and global warming (55%). Hence, it can be inferred from this that people are well aware about the global warming caused by the burning of fossil fuel through vehicle engines.

In every existing social problem, a debate arises whether the solution of the problem lies in the proper functioning of the governmental agencies or it depends upon the consciousness of the general population. To address this delicate issue about the pollution from vehicular pollution, **Question 9** was framed and the results are shown in **Table 12**. According to 52% of the respondents, the reduction in vehicular air pollution can be done through consciousness of general population and the rest 48%

think that the role of governmental agencies is important in reducing vehicular pollution. Looking closer to the response pattern, it can be inferred that in answering this particular question the sample population has been divided in equal parts. Hence, the debate remains - who is more responsible to reduce vehicular pollution. In the considered opinion of the researcher this can be achieved by a balanced combination of both of the two players.

Table 13 betrays the belief of the test sample population upon effective and stringent legal framework addressing the issue of vehicular pollution. In answering **Question 10**, large majority of the respondents have answered in a positive by holding opinion that stringent vehicular pollution laws can be effectively implemented by ensuring a non-corrupt and clean administration. This brings us to a very sensitive and delicate political issue of corruption within the administration responsible for implementing vehicular pollution laws. From the response it is seen that people do want a corruption-free and clean administration to act accordingly.

In our city of Kolkata, we have large variety of vehicles running from morning to next day morning. **Question 11** is an attempt to gather responses from the sample population about the nature of vehicles that according to their understanding are relatively more responsible for creating air pollution in the city. **Table 14** shows the response of the sample population, and from the response it is seen that people put blame more on the commercial vehicles for creating pollution through vehicular exhaust than the personal vehicles.

Question 12 in **Table 15** is rather a question regarding Governmental policy. This question asks whether the takeover of public transport system by the government can be a way to regulate and monitor vehicular pollution more efficiently. Almost half of the sample population believe that if the private transport system of the city is taken over by government agencies, then the pollution due to vehicular emission can be controlled more efficiently and effectively. And, it is to be mentioned here that almost another half of the sample population are not sure about governmental measures to regulate and monitor vehicular pollution more efficiently if they take over the public transport system. This may depict their disbelief regarding governmental set-up.

General people are not very much aware of the legal structure of our country. They are not very clear about various courts and tribunals etc constituted for various purposes locally and nationally. This is also confirmed from **Table 16**. In answering **Question 13**, 90% of the sample population have stated that there should be a separate

court or tribunal that should address the issue of vehicular pollution in the city of Kolkata. Whereas we know very well that there exists a bench of national Green Tribunal in our city which is competent to hear cases regarding vehicular pollution as well, the pattern of response of this question shows the lack of information among general public about the legal system in this particular area.

Table 17 records a very interesting observation through **Question 14**. It asks the sample population whether a decreasing the number of traffic signals within the city of Kolkata is a way to control vehicular pollution or not. 65% of the sample population have stated that decreasing the number of traffic signals within the city will not help to control pollution in Kolkata. At most of the traffic signals most of the running vehicles do not switch off their engines and that is why the city traffic signals are the most polluted points of the city. According to the researcher if the number of traffic signals is decreased and a clean way is created without the burden of traffic signals, the air pollution due to the vehicular emission may decrease a little bit.

Our national capital Delhi was the first city to introduce an odd-even principle to control vehicular pollution in the city. **Question 15** asks whether the same principle can be applied in the city of Kolkata as well to reduce vehicular pollution. **Table 18** shows that 66% of the sample population are unsure about this. Whereas 26% of the respondents believe that adopting an odd-even principle like Delhi can reduce vehicular air pollution in the city, and 9% of the respondents believe this will not help in reducing the said pollution. From the response pattern of this question, it can be inferred that as the system of odd even vehicles has not till date introduced in the city of Kolkata, the concept is not clear to the mass. If experimentally the system is introduced, then only we will be able to judge the effect of such principle.

Kolkata is a city of various types of vehicles, depending on the mode of transportation – whether it is through road or through waterways or through airways. **Question 16** is an attempt to bring out peoples' opinions regarding vehicular pollution from various modes of transportation. Majority of the respondents have answered that other than road transport, various transportation means are active in the city of Kolkata which may cause vehicular pollution. This is shown in **Table 19**.

Table 20 shows a Likert like response-sheet whereby a five-point scale was constituted through **Question 17** which asks whether the existing air pollution laws are sufficient to deal with the vehicular pollution in the city of Kolkata or not. 52% of the responses show that they disagree with the proposition made in the question. 18% of

the respondents strongly disagree with the proposition and 9% agree to the proposition. It is an important observation that none of the respondents strongly agree to the fact that there are existing laws which are sufficient to deal with the cooler air pollution in the city of Kolkata. 22% neutrality of the respondents show that they are not at all accustomed or informed about various laws regarding vehicular air pollution.

Question 18 shown in **Table 21** is a question testing the knowledge of the population regarding competent authority for monitoring and taking action regarding vehicular pollution in Kolkata. Whereas 74% of the respondents have recorded their response in favour of State Pollution Control Board, 11% and 14% of the response are in favour of Road Transport Department and Public Vehicles Department respectively. Hence, it can be safely inferred from this response pattern that mostly people are aware about the proper authority which is responsible for monitoring and taking action regarding vehicular pollution in Kolkata.

Question 19 again is a Likert-type question where the opinions of the people were sought regarding COVID-19 pandemic and lock down. 54% of the respondents agreed to the proposition that the nationwide lockdown in 2020 due to Covid 19 pandemic has improved the quality of air in Kolkata due to vehicular pollution. This is shown in **Table 22**.

The last question (**Question 20**) of this questionnaire shown in **Table 23** is a type of an abstract question where it was asked whether the justice system of vehicular pollution is anti-poor. 62% of the sample population think that it is anti-poor. This may be due to the fact that vehicle air pollution in walls of vehicles and vehicles are symbols of wealth. Hence, the justice system of vehicular pollution maybe antipode according to them.

SECTION – IX

Conclusion

From the above data analysis and the empirical study conducted by the researcher, it is seen that there is growing concern of the public for the devastating air pollution from vehicular emission. Although people are not well accustomed to or informed about various aspects of vehicular pollution, but this is normal. The chief aim of any social outreach program is to collect data from the society by selecting a sample population,

and then analyse the data to form hypotheses. In this study, too, a considerable size of sample was chosen and responses recorded to have a clear picture of the collective opinion of the people regarding the study. From the experience of the researcher, it can conveniently be commented that all the respondents participated voluntarily and with enthusiasm, and during the process of recording of responses, no personal data was collected from them. The questionnaire was made simple and easy to understand and was made in such a manner that no respondent can have any insecurity at the back of their mind that they are responding to a final year LL.M. study. No cumbersome legal terms were used intentionally and consciously, so that the questionnaire may make the respondents feel at home.

As for the subject matter of the study, it is a difficult task for any administration to fully comply with the various Acts, Rules, Directions and Orders issued in the interest of controlling and reducing air pollution due to vehicular emission, especially in a city like Kolkata. Majority of the roads and alleys were built in the British era, as the city of Kolkata is a very old city, and hence it is not possible to change that. Only thing is important that a balance of people's participation and governmental policy and timely stringent action would save the city from increasing vehicular air pollution.

The United Nations Conference on the Human Environment at Stockholm held between 5 to 16th June, 1972, made some declarations popularly known as the Stockholm Declaration, and it proclaimed in its declaration that:

Principle 6: *A point has been reached in history when we must shape our actions throughout the world with a more prudent care for their environmental consequences. Through ignorance or indifference, we can do massive and irreversible harm to the earthly environment on which our life and wellbeing depend. Conversely, through fuller knowledge and wiser action, we can achieve for ourselves and our posterity a better life in an environment more in keeping with human needs and hopes. There are broad vistas for the enhancement of environmental quality and the creation of a good life. What is needed is an enthusiastic but calm state of mind and intense but orderly work. For the purpose of attaining freedom in the world of nature, man must use knowledge to build, in collaboration with nature, a better environment. To defend and improve the human environment for present and future generations has become an imperative goal for mankind - a goal to be pursued together with, and in harmony*

with, the established and fundamental goals of peace and of worldwide economic and social development.

Principle 7: *To achieve this environmental goal will demand the acceptance of responsibility by citizens and communities and by enterprises and institutions at every level, all sharing equitably in common efforts. Individuals in all walks of life as well as organizations in many fields, by their values and the sum of their actions, will shape the world environment of the future. Local and national governments will bear the greatest burden for large-scale environmental policy and action within their jurisdictions. International cooperation is also needed in order to raise resources to support the developing countries in carrying out their responsibilities in this field. A growing class of environmental problems, because they are regional or global in extent or because they affect the common international realm, will require extensive cooperation among nations and action by international organizations in the common interest. The Conference calls upon Governments and peoples to exert common efforts for the preservation and improvement of the human environment, for the benefit of all the people and for their posterity.*

This says it all. If we are to make Kolkata a healthy city conducive for healthy living, then we must cooperate in all levels to achieve the proclamations made by the Stockholm Declaration. Not only the Governmental agencies, we, the members of the ordinary public should be conscious enough to combat air pollution due to vehicular pollution. Many cities in the world are starting to incentivise cycling as a major option for commuting, like the Netherlands. In India also, there are various app-based services that rent out bicycles and they are of minimum cost. In this era of increasing fuel prices and polluting cities, we must care for ourselves as well as our coming generations. Thus, we can shift towards pollution-free commuting if that is possible for us. We must not use fossil fuel-based vehicles for short distance travelling and for daily commuting purposes. The Government should also plan cycle lanes for commuting along with roads and highways. Many Indian states have done that so far, like Tamilnadu or Maharashtra. Thus, it is a shared responsibility for us all.